

Preparation, properties, spectral (IR, electronic, FAB-MS and PXRD) and magnetic characterization of some lanthanide complexes containing tridentate thiosemicarbazone ligand

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Abstract : Schiff bases, containing 'S' donor atom, such as benzophenonethiosemicarbazone (btscH), salicylidene-thiosemicarbazone (stscH) and bis-salicylidene-thiosemicarbazone (bstscH) have been reacted with methanolic solution of $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ and Ce^{III}) followed by addition of the saturated solution of KOH (in EtOH) in different molar ratio(s), afforded a variety of lanthanum(III) chloride Schiff base complexes of the type, $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ln}(\text{L}) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{ClLn}(\text{L})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (where $\text{L} = \text{btscH}$, stscH , bstscH and $\text{Ln} = \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ and Ce^{III}). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, spectral (IR, UV-Visible and FAB-mass) as well as magnetic studies. X-Ray powder diffraction on two of the complex was recorded on Rigaku Model D/Max-2200 PC using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$, radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The crystallite size of the complexes $[\text{ClLa}(\text{bstsc})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (6) and $[\text{ClCe}(\text{bstsc})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (12) were found to be 280 and 191 \AA respectively. On the basis of these physico-chemical data a tentative structure for these complexes have been proposed. These complexes were found to be solid and were soluble in Lewis bases such as in DMF and DMSO or pyridine.

Keywords : Lanthanum(III), cerium(III) chloride, Schiff base complex, FAB-MS, IR studies, PXRD analysis.

Introduction

Coordination chemistry of lanthanide with Schiff bases constitutes a versatile class of compounds with biological applications¹⁻³. Much interest has been shown in them partly because rare earth elements can form complexes of variable coordination numbers⁴. Lanthanide complexes show biological activities^{5,6}, pharmacological activities^{7,8} and antibacterial properties⁹. Thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes have played a wide range of biological properties. Due to this a large number of transition metal complexes of thiosemicarbazones have been reported¹⁰⁻¹². The multidentate nature of Schiff bases and its versatility in showing higher coordination number of lanthanide ions attracted us (i) to carry out the studies on lanthanide complexes of Schiff bases and (ii) the coordination behavior of Schiff bases towards lanthanide, due to its behavior as hard acids and these are expected to form stronger complexes with ligands containing 'O', 'N' and 'S' donor atoms¹³⁻¹⁶. Therefore, it is worthwhile to investigate the nature of these ligands, whether it behave

in bidentate or tridentate fashion. In view of the above interesting properties of lanthanides, we report herein, the syntheses and structural elucidation {by means of elemental analysis, molar conductance, spectral (IR, UV-Visible, FAB-mass) and magnetic studies} of some lanthanide(III) chloride Schiff base complexes in which the sulphur atom is in coordination alongwith nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms present in the ligands.

Materials and methods : The metal(III) chlorides, $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{Ln} = \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ and Ce^{III}) (Loba) used as such for the syntheses of lanthanide complexes. All the solvents used were purified by standard procedure¹⁷. The metal was determined as lanthanum oxide, Ln_2O_3 after destroying the organic matter by using fuming HNO_3 several times. Chloride was determined by using Volhard's method¹⁸. Molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMSO (10^{-3} M) solution using a coronation digital conductivity method. FAB-mass spectra of complexes were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the

FAB gas. The IR spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded in KBr discs on a FTIR-5300 spectrophotometer, in 4000–200 cm^{-1} range, magnetic moment was measured on a Guoy-balance using $\text{Hg}\{\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4\}$ as calibrant and was further corrected for diamagnetism using Pascal's constant. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer. X-Ray powder diffraction of the complex was recorded on a Rigaku Model D/Max-2200 PC using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$).

Preparation of ligands :

The ligand is prepared by standard procedure¹⁹

(Schemes 1 and 2) salicylidene-thiosemicarbazone was prepared by reacting thiosemicarbazone (5.96 g; 65.42 mmol) dissolved in methanol in presence of glacial acetic acid (~3 drops) with salicylaldehyde (8.0 g; 65.42 mmol) and stirred (~1 h), refluxed (~4 h). The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature to afford white crystals, which was recrystallized in ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The analytically pure white crystal of the ligand was obtained.

Synthesis of complex :

A general procedure was adopted to synthesize the

Scheme 1. Synthesis of lanthanide metal complexes with Schiff bases (btscH).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of lanthanide metal complexes with Schiff bases.

complexes as given : The methanolic solution of hydrated lanthanum chloride (LnCl₃.7H₂O) was added to the methanolic solution of Schiff base (stscH) in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s), followed by the addition of saturated ethanolic solution of KOH, during which time cream colour precipitate was obtained. Further, it was refluxed for several hours (~20 h). The excess of solvent was removed by distillation and followed by addition of pet-ether to extract the solid complexes of the types, [Cl₂Ln(L).4H₂O]

and [ClLn(L)₂.3H₂O]. The precipitate was filtered off and dried *in vacuo*. The crude product was washed several times with ethanol to remove any unreacted metal chloride. Further, it was washed with diethyl ether. The pure product was dried *in vacuo* over P₄O₁₀. The compounds of same stoichiometry were obtained, when the cerium chloride and ligand were reacted in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios under similar condition. For the sake of brevity details of all the complexes are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. Synthetic physical and analytical data of lanthanum(III) and cerium(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex (% yield)	Molecular formula	Physical state and colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						D.p (°C)
				C	H	N	Ln/Ce	Cl	S	
1.	[Cl ₂ La(btsc).4H ₂ O] (47)	[C ₁₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ LaN ₃ O ₄ S]	Light green, powdery solid	31.32 (31.36)	3.65 (3.76)	7.76 (7.84)	25.84 (25.91)	13.15 (13.22)	5.89 (5.98)	320
2.	[Cl ₂ La(stsc).4H ₂ O] (75)	[C ₈ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ LaN ₃ O ₅ S]	Yellow, powdery solid	20.10 (20.18)	3.30 (3.39)	8.79 (8.83)	29.13 (29.18)	14.78 (14.89)	6.66 (6.73)	295
3.	[Cl ₂ La(bstsc).4H ₂ O] (42)	[C ₁₅ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ LaN ₃ O ₆ S]	Dirty white, powdery solid	30.00 (31.05)	3.38 (3.47)	7.16 (7.24)	23.91 (23.94)	12.02 (12.22)	5.16 (5.53)	251
4.	[ClLa(btsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (49)	[C ₂₈ H ₃₀ ClLaN ₆ O ₃ S ₂]	Brown, powdery solid	45.55 (45.63)	4.05 (4.10)	11.34 (11.40)	18.80 (18.85)	4.72 (4.81)	8.61 (8.70)	> 360
5.	[ClLa(stsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (83)	[C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ClLaN ₆ O ₅ S ₂]	Canary yellow, powdery solid	31.10 (31.15)	3.48 (3.59)	10.32 (10.40)	22.44 (22.52)	5.55 (5.75)	10.38 (10.40)	> 360
6.	[ClLa(bstsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (88)	[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ ClLaN ₆ O ₇ S ₂]	Dark yellow, powdery solid	43.61 (43.67)	3.41 (3.66)	10.15 (10.19)	16.79 (16.84)	4.22 (4.30)	7.23 (7.77)	245
7.	[Cl ₂ Ce(btsc).4H ₂ O] (49)	[C ₁₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ CeN ₃ O ₄ S]	Dirty brown, powdery solid	31.25 (31.29)	3.64 (3.75)	7.23 (7.28)	26.01 (26.07)	13.13 (13.19)	5.83 (5.98)	320
8.	[Cl ₂ Ce(stsc).4H ₂ O] (58)	[C ₈ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ CeN ₃ O ₅ S]	Light brown, powdery solid	20.05 (20.13)	3.30 (3.38)	8.74 (8.80)	29.25 (29.35)	14.83 (14.86)	6.70 (6.72)	170-173
9.	[Cl ₂ Ce(bstsc).4H ₂ O] (48)	[C ₁₅ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ LaN ₃ O ₆ S]	Light brown, powdery solid	30.86 (30.99)	3.35 (3.47)	7.08 (7.23)	24.05 (24.10)	12.10 (12.20)	5.45 (5.51)	320
10.	[ClCe(btsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (48)	[C ₂₈ H ₃₀ ClCeN ₆ O ₃ S ₂]	Light brown, powdery solid	45.42 (45.55)	4.02 (4.10)	11.31 (11.38)	18.84 (18.98)	4.69 (4.80)	8.62 (8.69)	360
11.	[ClCe(stsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (60)	[C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ClCeN ₆ O ₅ S ₂]	Chocolate color, powdery solid	31.00 (31.09)	3.49 (3.59)	13.50 (13.60)	22.61 (22.67)	5.57 (5.74)	10.27 (10.38)	360
12.	[ClCe(bstsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O] (50)	[C ₃₀ H ₃₀ ClCeN ₆ O ₇ S ₂]	Brownish black, powdery solid	43.48 (43.61)	3.52 (3.66)	9.98 (10.17)	16.88 (16.96)	4.17 (4.29)	7.68 (7.76)	225-228

Results and discussion

Lanthanum chloride (LnCl₃.7H₂O) react with Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s) to produce various complexes, such as [Cl₂Ln(L).4H₂O] and [ClLn(L)₂.3H₂O] as shown in the following chemical equations :

(where Ln = La^{III} and Ce^{III}, and L = btscH, stscH, btscH)

When reaction was carried out in 1 : 3 : 3 molar ratio, desired product could not be obtained. Only 1 : 2 : 2

products could be isolated and further identified by elemental analysis.

All the complexes are insoluble in water, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, benzene, acetone, dichloromethane and acetonitrile. However, they are soluble in Lewis bases such as in DMF and DMSO or pyridine. The molar conductivity value in DMF/DMSO at 25 °C indicates a non-electrolytic nature of the complex. The complexes are air stable and decompose at around 332-360 °C. All these solid complexes of lanthanum(III) are diamagnetic at room temperature as expected for 4f⁰ system, whereas cerium(III) chloride complexes of Schiff bases exhibit their magnetic moment in the range 2.35 ± 0.5 BM as expected for cerium(III) system.

Molar conductance :

The complexes were dissolved in DMSO (dimethylsulphoxide) solution and their molar conductivity was determined with DMSO as a reference. The values of molar conductivity are less than $40 \text{ S cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating that complexes are non-electrolyte in DMSO^{19a}.

Infrared spectral studies :

The IR spectrum of ligands exhibited characteristic band in the region $3453\text{--}3353 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ stretching frequency^{20,21} and in the range $1627\text{--}1611 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibrations due to coordination in complexes these bands shifted to lower frequency region $1608\text{--}1581 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This negative shift shows the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in the coordination²².

In the complexes, $[\text{CfLa}(\text{stsc})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{CfLa}(\text{bstsc})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ce}(\text{stsc}) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ce}(\text{bstsc}) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ the peaks observed due to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ in the range $1368\text{--}1312 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicate that the bonding take place through phenolic oxygen after the deprotonation of -OH group. In free ligands these peaks were in the range of $1278\text{--}1269 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ²³. The band at $1365\text{--}1353 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is blue shifted to $778\text{--}752 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes indicating the coordination through, sulphur atom of $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ group²⁴. The bands at $3100\text{--}3040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (aromatic NH_2) in the ligand (stscH and bstscH) remains unchanged in the complexes which indicates the non participation of -NH_2 group in coordination/bonding with metal ions²⁵. Lanthanum(III) complexes showed IR frequencies in the range $472\text{--}454 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $576\text{--}544 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which have been assigned for $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{La-O}}$ respectively²⁶.

IR spectra of all the complexes exhibited a broad band in the region $3360\text{--}3420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be ascribed to ν_{OH} stretching frequencies, spectra of the complexes after drying at around $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ show shift in this band to be at $\sim 3320\text{--}3340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of coordinated water.

Electronic spectral studies :

The electronic spectrum of lanthanides constituting mainly by Laporte-forbidden, $4f$ transitions^{27,28} are not much influenced by ligand environment, as in the case of 'd' block elements. Moeller *et al.*²⁷ observed three general effects in the absorption spectra of rare earth metal complexes as compared to those of aquated metal ions : (i) small shifts, usually towards longer wave lengths and rarely towards shorter wave lengths, (ii) splitting of certain bands in to several small area and (iii) changes in specific absorptivity of an individual absorption peak. The absorption is not effected by the coordination of the metal ion.

The absorption bands observed between 25000 and 16650 cm^{-1} for the complexes studied herein show an increase in the molar absorption coefficient as compared to those of lanthanum in methanol. Further, the band at $\sim 20900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of complexes shows a red shift from 20620 cm^{-1} absorption. This type of differences in electronic spectra of lanthanide complexes indicates very weak covalent bond between ligand and trivalent lanthanide ions.

FAB-mass studies :

The FAB-mass spectrum (Fig. 1) and the fragmenta-

Fig. 1. FAB-mass spectrum of $[\text{CfLa}(\text{bstsc})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (6).

Scheme 3. Mass fragmentation pattern of $[ClLa(bstsc)_2 \cdot 3H_2O]^+$ (6).

tion pattern²⁹⁻³¹ of the complexes, [ClLa(bstsc)₂.3H₂O] (**6**) and [ClCe(bstsc)₂.3H₂O] (**12**) gives a tentative idea about the molecular weight and molecular formula of these complexes. The molecular ion peak (M⁺) along with some characteristic peaks showing various fragmentations were observed for these complexes; which convincingly support the composition of these interesting new complexes.

The FAB-mass spectrum of the complex [ClLa(bstsc)₂.3H₂O] (**6**) exhibited characteristic molecular ion peak at 825 (*m/z*), suggests the monomeric nature of the complex (Scheme 3). The molecular ion peak observed at 771 (*m/z*) corresponds to the formula [ClLaC₃₀H₂₄N₆O₄S₂] after elimination of 3H₂O. Successive fragmentation produced many more important peaks, due to the formation of

-OH[•], -C₆H₄[•], -C₂NH[•], -CS[•], -C₇H₅O[•], -CSNH[•], -N₃H[•], -Cl[•], -NH[•] radicals, which confirms the structures of the complex.

On the basis of spectral and other physico-chemical data the coordination number of lanthanum(III) ions is tentatively assigned to 8-10 as proposed in Scheme 3.

X-Ray powder diffraction studies :

X-Ray diffraction (PXRD) were carried out on Rigaku Model D/Max-2200 PC diffractometer instrument operating with Cu-K α , radiation ($\lambda = 1.540556 \text{ \AA}$). The powder XRD patterns³² of complexes (**6**) and (**12**) were recorded in the 2 θ range between 20-80 °C which has shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The average crystallite size was calculated from the diffraction line width based on

Fig. 2. PXRD of [ClLa(bstsc)₂.3H₂O].

Fig. 3. PXRD of [ClCe(bstsc)₂.3H₂O].

Table 2. Calculated XRD parameters of lanthanum(III) and cerium(III) complex

Parameters	[ClLa(bstsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O]	[ClCe(bstsc) ₂ .3H ₂ O]
Crystallite size (Å)	280	191
Empirical formula	[ClC ₃₀ H ₃₀ LaN ₆ O ₇ S ₂]	[ClC ₃₀ H ₃₀ CeN ₆ O ₇ S ₂]
Formula weight	825	826
Powder used (Kw)	1.6	1.6
Wavelength (Å)	1.540	1.540

the Scherrer relation. Spectrum clearly showed that the materials prepared are crystalline in nature. Non uniform broadening of lines is attracted to isotopic crystallites. The line broadening is used here to calculate the crystallite size (Table 2) using Debye-Scherrers formula.

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